

ABOUT MATHEMATICAL AND PHYSICAL MODELS OF SOME COUNTRY PROBLEMS

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ABSTRACT

The article presents a scheme for determining the kinetic energy of a projectile during drilling based on certain laws of mathematics and physics.

A high school math teacher is often asked by students in lectures or practical classes, "Where is this or that knowledge gained in lectures applied in practice?". has to answer the constant question of.

In order to answer similar questions from mining students, it is advisable to move from abstract examples to solving problems related to mining production, thus demonstrating the need for knowledge of mathematics and physics.

This method of training allows you to achieve two goals:

- Students majoring in "Mining" expand their knowledge in this area;
- Increased interest in mathematics and physics.

In the examples of solving problems on drilling, we consider the application of the laws of mathematics and physics.

Drilling is the process of creating artificial cylindrical depths (cavities, boreholes and wells) in a rock massif using drilling machines. In this case, there are three methods of mechanical drilling on the nature of the interaction of the machine tool: percussion, rotary drilling with shear, percussion-rotary, rotary-percussion. We will focus on percussive drilling of wells, and in its example we will consider the motion of the whole universe of gravity, because in this case the operation of the drilling shell is based on the rules of free fall caused by gravity.

Question 1. A drilling rig with a mass of 2,500 kg rises to a height of 1.2 m using a crankshaft (balancing) mechanism on the well site and descends freely again. During the descent, the doloto blade crushes the rocks at the well site. Well diameter $d = 0.250$ m, rock density 2600 kg / m^3 . Find out:

- a) the kinetic energy of the projectile during impact;
- b) energy used to vibrate the soil;
- c) energy spent on deformation (crushing) of rocks;
- g) the efficiency of the projectile. The impact should be considered inelastic.

During forging, the shells interact with the rocks, which allows them to be considered as a whole and called a “shell-rock” system.

On descent, the drilling shell accumulates kinetic energy under the influence of gravity. As a result of the impulse interaction of the shell with the rock, not only its crushing but also its vibration (vibration) occurs. Since the drilling shell and the rocks form a whole system during the interaction, the kinetic energy accumulated by the projectile is used within this system not only to decompose but also to vibrate the rock (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Diagram of kinetic energy distribution of a drilling projectile:

T_1 – the kinetic energy of the projectile during impact; T_2 , T_3 – energy expended on the deformation (crushing) and vibration (vibration) of rocks.

We find the kinetic energy T_1 of the projectile during impact by the following

formula:

$$T_1 = \frac{m_1 V_1^2}{2}$$

(1)

here, m_1 - shell mass, $m_1 = 2500$ kg;

V_1 - projectile velocity during tattooing.

We determine the velocity of the projectile during impact by the formula:

$$V_1^2 = 2gh \tag{2}$$

here, h - shell drop height, $h=1,2$ m;

g - free fall acceleration; $g= 9,8$ m/c².

After substituting certain values for (1), we obtain:

$$T_1 = \frac{2500(2 \cdot 9,8 \cdot 1,2)^2}{2} = 691500J$$

To determine the energy expended on the vibration of rocks, we find the velocity of the "shell-rock" system in advance after the direct impact. To do this, the law of conservation of momentum is applied, according to which the amount of motion in a closed system remains unchanged, and the inelastic shock of two

bodies is represented by the following formula:

$$m_1V_1 + m_2V_2 = (m_1 + m_2)U \tag{3}$$

here, V_2 - the velocity of the rocks before the helmet, $V_1= 0$, because the rocks before the tattoo are at rest;

m_2 - mass of rocks exposed to drilling shells;

U - mass of rocks exposed to drilling shells;

Since the shell and the rock move as a whole at the same speed after an interacting impulse in an inelastic shock, we determine this U velocity from $V_1 = 0$ and determine from the following expression:

$$U = \frac{m_1}{m_1 + m_2} V_1 \tag{4}$$

The limit of hardness of rocks to compression, MPa

Figure-2. Table of dependence of drilling productivity SBSH-250 MN on compression of rocks of different diameters on limits of hardness of rocks

As a result of the interaction of the drilling projectile with the rock, part of its kinetic energy is transferred to the "shell-rock" system, under the influence of which it moves rapidly. Such a shift in the system

is manifested by the vibration of the rocks, and the energy expended on vibration (vibration) can be determined by the following formula:

$$T_2 = \frac{(m_1 + m_2)U^2}{2} \quad (5)$$

In (5) we replace the velocity U with its value in (4) and we get (2):

$$T_2 = \frac{(m_1 + m_2)}{2} \left(\frac{m_1}{m_1 + m_2} V_1 \right)^2 = \frac{m_1^2}{2(m_1 + m_2)} V_1^2 = \frac{m_1^2}{2(m_1 + m_2)} \frac{2m_2 g^2 h^2}{m_1 + m_2} \quad (6)$$

We determine the mass per m2 of the rock section interacting with the drilling rig as follows. Based on the percussion drilling experience, we assume that this section of rock consists of a column (cylinder) with a diameter of Du and a height of Nu on three diameters of the drilling rig [1], that is $D_y = H_y = 3 \cdot 0,25 \text{ m} = 0,75 \text{ m}$. Then $\rho = 2600 \text{ kg}$ of rock density, $D = 0,25 \text{ m}$ in diameter is as follows:

$$m_2 = \rho \pi \frac{D_y^2}{4} H_y = 2600 \cdot 3,14 \frac{0,75^2}{4} = 860 \text{ kg}$$

Then

$$T_2 = \frac{2 \cdot 2500^2 \cdot 9,81^2 \cdot 1,2^2}{2500 + 860} = 486130 \text{ J}$$

Thus, the drilling shell has T1 energy before impact, from which T2 goes to the vibration (vibration) of the rock. Accordingly, the energy expended in the decomposition of rocks is as follows:

$$T_3 = T_1 - T_2 = 691500 - 486130 \approx 205370 \text{ J}$$

The T3 energy used to break down rocks should be considered useful energy. In it, the FIC of the drilling rig in the impact drilling of the well is as follows:

$$\eta = \frac{T_3}{T_1} 100 = \frac{205370}{691500} 100 = 29,7\%$$

Thus, the considered example allows us to conclude that the efficiency of the drilling rig in percussive drilling is very low and depends mainly on the mass of the drill shell m1 and, to a lesser extent, the mass of m2 of rock exposed to impact. Exactly because of the lack of FIC, the method of conducting wells using a falling drilling rig is almost never used at present.

Question 2. In the example of drilling (2) wells with a shaft drilling rig, we consider the motion of the law of conservation of energy (Fig. 2). In the case under consideration, the action of this law is manifested when the energy expended by the rig drive on rock erosion is a constant quantity (magnitude) because the drilling rig cannot consume more energy than the engine power installed for this purpose. Therefore, when drilling conditions change, such as well diameter or physical and mechanical properties of rocks, the drilling speed of wells also changes. In particular, as the diameter of the well decreases, the specific power of the drive per unit of drilling tool increases. Accordingly, the portion of the rock affected by the drilling tool may also increase. The result is an increase in drilling productivity (speed).

A similar phenomenon is observed in changes in the physical and mechanical properties of eroded rocks. In particular, an increase in the hardness limit of the rocks requires an increase in the force on the drilling tool to break them down, which is not possible because the drive will have a defined power. It is therefore necessary to reduce the portion of the rock to be eroded using a drilling tool to generate the stress required for erosion. Naturally, this leads to a decrease in drilling productivity (speed).

Mathematical interrelationships of driving power, diameter of drilling rig, physical and mechanical properties of drilling and productivity are given in the form of expressions [2]:

$$Q_6 = \frac{0,1 \cdot N_{ep} \cdot K_{з.дв}}{e^{0,017} \cdot \sigma_{сж} \cdot D_i^2}$$

here, Q_6 – drilling productivity (speed), m / s);

N_{ep} – drilling tool power, kW;

$K_{з.дв}$ – engine load factor;

D_i – well diameter, m;

$\sigma_{сж}$ – compressive strength of rocks, MPa;

$e = 2,72$ – natural logarithm basis.

When drilling wells with a diameter of $D1 = 0.2$ m, $D2 = 0.25$ m, $D3 = 0.27$ m, we

determine the change in the productivity of the drilling rig SBSH-250 MN. Assume that the engine load factor is $K_{з.дв} = 0.9$. Drilling rig power of SBSH-250 MN is $N_{pr} = 68$ kW. The results obtained describe (demonstrate) the relationship between the diameter of the well and the physical and mechanical properties of the rocks and the drilling productivity when the drilling rig's constant power changes (Figure 2).

The analysis of the obtained tables again allows us to conclude that as the compression rock hardness limit increases, the well drilling speed tends to a certain limit, which can be changed only by changing (increasing) the driving force.

References:

1. М.Г.Новожилов и др."Технология открытой разработки месторождений полезных ископаемых"Изд."Недра",Москва 1971г
2. Е.А.Толстов, В.Н.Сытенков, С.А.Филлипов "Процессы открытой разработки рудных месторождений в скальных массивах"Изд."Фан", Ташкент 1999г.
3. Khakimov A., Ismoilova Z. T.,Kushmurotov U. I.,Kushmurotova N. I. "Train traffic rectangular final length" ВЕСТНИК НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ 2020. № 7 (85). Часть 6-10стр.
4. Kushmurotov U. I. "Bo'lg'usi konchi muxandislariga matematika o'qitish samaradorligini oshirishda fanlararo aloqalar haqida"«Глобальная наука и инновация 2020:центральная азия» № 5(10). август 2020 серия «педагогические науки» журнал основан в 2018 г.